

**MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE (BIODEGRADABLE)
MANAGEMENT**

SUBMITTED BY

ASHUTOSH DESHPANDE

D-050114

B.TECH (Civil Engineering)

2008-2009

Guided by

Dr. P. P. BHAVE

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering

Veermata Jijabai Technological Institute

(Autonomous Institute Affiliated to University of Mumbai)

Mumbai 400019

2008-2009

CONTENTS

1] Introduction –	2
2] Scope of Work –	5
3] Need for Project –	6
4] Principles of MSW Management –	8
5] Objectives –	10
6] Literature Review –	11
i) Municipal Solid Waste –	18
ii) Contents of MSW –	19
iii) Functional Elements of MSW –	25
iv) Concepts in MSW Management –	29
7] Methodology –	
A] Composting -	33
B] Vermicomposting -	48
Advantages of Vermicompost –	77
How to Use Vermicompost –	78
8] Conclusion -	79
References -	80

INTRODUCTION

Solid Waste Management is one of the essential obligatory functions of the Urban Local Bodies in India. This service is falling too short of the desired level of efficiency and satisfaction resulting in problems of health, sanitation and environmental degradation. Most urban areas in the country are plagued by acute problems related to solid waste. Due to lack of serious efforts by town/city authorities, garbage and its management has become a tenacious problem and this notwithstanding the fact that the largest part of municipal expenditure is allotted to it. Barring a few progressive municipal corporations in the country, most local bodies suffer due to non-availability of adequate expertise and experience, thereby the solid waste is not properly handled resulting into creation of environmental pollution and health hazards. It is reiterated that the local bodies lack technical, managerial, administrative, financial and adequate institutional arrangements.

In every urban centre, huge quantity of solid waste is generated during various activities. These wastes are to be stored, collected, transported, processed and disposed of in an environment friendly manner, so as to keep the city neat and clean. In spite of incurring huge expenditure, the services that are provided to the solid waste management are not fulfilling the requirement, causing public health hazards and nuisance. Hence, there is a strong need to develop appropriate technology for the proper management of urban solid wastes. MSW Management includes generation, collection, storage, transfer and transport, processing and disposal of solid wastes in a manner that suits best to public without affecting the economics, engineering, conservation health, aesthetics and other environmental Considerations.

Solid waste management is a large ongoing, vital public system spread over the entire city area and the system is responsible for maintaining the public surroundings. Hence, the system has to be planned rationally for a long and short term. Moreover, as the system handles huge quantities of solid waste, it is necessary to have detailed information on quantification and characterization of solid waste for proper handling of solid waste at different stages of the system. Presently, majority of Municipal Corporations/ Councils do not weigh their waste but the quantities are estimated on the basis of number of trips of trucks which carry the waste to disposal site. Moreover, the solid waste management system is not planned or executed rationally due to non-availability of authentic or relevant information on waste generation. As the solid waste quantities are increasing in all cities and towns due to urbanization and industrialization, these have raised concerns about the economic viability and environmental compatibility of the current waste management methodologies.

On one hand tropical soils are deficient in all necessary plant nutrients and on the other hand large quantities of such nutrients contained in domestic wastes and agricultural byproducts are wasted. It is estimated that in cities and rural areas of India nearly 700 million tonnes organic wastes is generated annually which is either burned or land filled. Such large quantities of organic wastes generated also pose a problem for safe disposal. Most of these organic residues are burned currently or used as land fillings. In nature's laboratory there are a number of organisms (micro and macro) that have the ability to convert organic waste into valuable resources containing plant nutrients and organic matter, which are critical for maintaining soil productivity. Microorganisms and earthworms are important

biological organisms helping nature to maintain nutrient flows from one system to another and also minimize environmental degradation.

Municipal Solid Waste Management includes generation, collection, storage, transfer and transport, processing and disposal of solid wastes in a manner that suits best to public without affecting the economics, engineering, conservation health, aesthetics and other environmental considerations.

FIG : CHIEF COMPONENTS OF MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

SCOPE OF WORK

The project involves comparative study for processes of Municipal Solid (Biodegradable) Waste disposal. This will require constructions of two pits namely for Vermicomposting and for Aerobic Composting. Further the total solid waste generated at VJTI Hostels will be gathered and their classification will be carried out. The characteristics of waste will also be determined. This will enable to reduce the waste and ensure its safe disposal thereby generating eco-friendly and sound systems, strengthening the biological system.

- Comparative study for Municipal Solid Waste Disposal.
- Quantity of solid waste generated at VJTI Hostels and classification of waste.
- Characteristic determination of Hostel Generated Solid Waste.
- Establishment of an Aerobic Composting and Vermicomposting plant in VJTI Hostel Premises.
- To reduce the waste to give eco-friendly and environmentally sound systems and to strengthen the eco-logical systems

NEED FOR PROJECT

Many a times a large quantity of Vegetable waste lies unattended in the waste pit for 3 to 4 days due to carelessness of waste collecting authorities. This results into a number of problems like odour and insects nuisance in the premises of the Hostel. Due to lack of serious efforts by town/city authorities, garbage and its management has become a tenacious problem and this notwithstanding the fact that the largest part of municipal expenditure is allotted to it. There has been a progressive decline in the standard of services with respect to collection and disposal of municipal solid waste as well as measures for ensuring adequacy of environmental sanitation and public hygiene.

It is estimated that on an average about 150 kg of waste is generated from each mess in the VJTI Hostels. It is also estimated that the Hostel spends about Rs.3000 to Rs.5000 on collection, transportation, treatment and disposal of this waste to the BrihanMumbai Municipal Corporation.

Waste Management is a complex task which depends as much upon organization and cooperation between households, communities, private enterprises and municipal authorities as it does upon the selection and application of appropriate technical solutions for waste collection, transfer, recycling and disposal. At many places, waste management is inadequate: a significant portion of the population does not have access to a waste collection service and only a fraction of the generated waste is actually collected.

Systems for transfer, recycling and/or disposal of solid waste are unsatisfactory from the environmental, economic and financial points of view.

Waste should be managed in ways that protect human health and the environment and in particular:

- ✓ Without risk to water, air, soil and plants and animals;
- ✓ Without causing a nuisance through noise or odors;
- ✓ Without adversely affecting the countryside or places of special interest;
- ✓ Disposing of waste at the nearest appropriate installation, by means of the most appropriate methods and technologies.

PRINCIPLES OF MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE **MANAGEMENT**

THE FOUR BASIC PRINCIPLES OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

REDUCE: -

The amount of waste that goes to the waste bin.

REUSE

Plastic and metal containers can be reused for various activities. The waste from residents includes organic waste, which can be composted and can be used as manure by the plants in the garden. Solid waste especially MSW contains non-biodegradable plastics which found to be major problem for disposal. These types of plastics block the drains and create problem to the surrounding. Especially plastics of less than 10 micron cannot be recycled. These type plastics were banned but due to high cost of biodegradable plastics the usage of the later type of plastic became unavoidable

RECYCLE

Segregate the waste materials and send the materials that can be recycled to recycling unit. Eg. Plastics can be recycled to form new products; the organic waste can be composted to bio-fertilizer or can be used in landfill gas recovery; organic waste can be used to produce biogas through bio-methanation process. Dried organic waste and waste from industries can be briquetted. Excess heat from industries, which is considered as form of waste can be converted to other form of energy by heating the boiler through cogeneration process.

RESPOND

Create awareness among public about ill-effect of open waste disposal and educate about the diseases and remedies. Encourage new ideas that can reduce the waste disposal.

The principles of waste management strategies are thus to develop an insight into the impact of waste generation, collection, transportation and disposal methods adopted by a society on the environment and to adopt new methods to reduce this impact.

In other words,

- ✓ Minimize waste generation
- ✓ Maximize waste recycling and reuse, and
- ✓ Ensure the safe and environmentally sound disposal of waste.

OBJECTIVES

1. Improve the way that waste is managed by:

- ✓ Moving the management of waste up the waste hierarchy, by reducing and recycling more and disposing of less.
- ✓ Managing waste in a way that takes account of the potential needs of future generations.
- ✓ Taking action to avoid serious or irreversible environmental damage.
- ✓ Maximizing opportunities to turn waste products into resources.
- ✓ Managing waste at the nearest appropriate waste management facility where possible within the county boundaries.
- ✓ Managing waste by means of the most appropriate methods and technologies.
- ✓ Managing waste in a way that is consistent with legislation and anticipating where possible future legislative changes.
- ✓ Managing waste in a way that avoids endangering human health and harm to the environment.

2. Increase the amount of waste we recycle/compost without increasing the waste stream by:

- ✓ Ensuring that accessible and viable services and facilities are available to residents.
- ✓ Providing a collection for two recyclable materials to all households.
- ✓ Promoting and encouraging design and layout of new developments that support sustainable waste management (eg encouraging construction of recycling areas).

3. Manage our remaining waste in an appropriate way, by:

- ✓ Reducing the amount we landfill.
- ✓ Aiming to recover value of waste (recycling and energy recovery together).

LITERATURE REVIEW

WASTE:

Any material which is not needed by the owner, producer or processor is called as waste.

SOLID WASTE:

The American Public association categorizes Solid Wastes as refuse, including “semi-liquid or wet wastes with insufficient moisture and other liquid contents to be free-flowing”. Solid Waste is that normally solid material arising from natural, animal or human life and activities and discarded permanently or temporarily as waste. It also includes deposited waste particulates temporarily suspended in air or water. Solid wastes are the organic and inorganic waste materials.

DEFINITIONS AND CLASSIFICATION OF SOLID WASTES

In order to plan, design and operate a solid waste management system, a thorough knowledge of the quantities generated the composition of wastes and its characteristics are essential. As a first step, a proper definition of the terms is necessary to avoid the general confusion that is common in the usage of these terms.

DEFINITIONS

There are many terms, which relate to the types and sources of wastes and these too must be defined. Based on the source, origin and type of waste a comprehensive classification is described below:

(i) Domestic/Residential Waste:

This category of waste comprises the solid wastes that originate from single and multi-family household units. These wastes are generated as a consequence of household activities such as cooking, cleaning, repairs, hobbies, redecoration, empty containers, packaging, clothing, old books, writing/new paper, and old furnishings. Households also discard bulky wastes such as furniture and large appliances which cannot be repaired and used.

(ii) Municipal Waste:

Municipal waste includes wastes resulting from municipal activities and services such as street waste, dead animals, market waste and abandoned vehicles. However, the term is commonly applied in a wider sense to incorporate domestic wastes, institutional wastes and commercial wastes.

(iii) Commercial Waste:

Included in this category are solid wastes that originate in offices, wholesale and retail stores, restaurants, hotels, markets, warehouses and other commercial establishments. Some of these wastes are further classified as garbage and others as rubbish.

(iv) Institutional Waste:

Institutional wastes are those arising from institutions such as schools, universities, hospitals and research institutes. It includes wastes which are classified as garbage and rubbish as well as wastes which are considered to be hazardous to public health and to the environment.

(v) Garbage:

Garbage is the term applied to animal and vegetable wastes resulting from the handling, storage, sale, preparation, cooking and serving of food. Such wastes contain putrescible organic matter, which produces strong odours and therefore attracts rats, flies and other vermin. It requires immediate attention in its storage, handling and disposal.

(vi) Rubbish:

Rubbish is a general term applied to solid wastes originating in households, commercial establishments and institutions, excluding garbage and ashes.

(vii) Ashes:

Ashes are the residues from the burning of wood, coal, charcoal, coke and other combustible materials, for cooking and heating in houses, institutions and small industrial establishments. When produced in large quantities at power generating plants and factories these wastes are classified as industrial wastes. Ashes consist of a fine powdery residue, cinders and clinker often mixed with small pieces of metal and glass.

(viii) Bulky Wastes:

In this category are bulky household wastes which cannot be accommodated in the normal storage containers of households. For this reason they require special collection. In developed countries bulky wastes are large household appliances such as cookers, refrigerators and washing machines as well as furniture, crates, vehicle parts, tyres, wood, trees and branches. Metallic bulky wastes are sold as scrap metal but some portion is disposed of at sanitary landfills.

(ix) Street Sweeping:

This term applies to wastes that are collected from streets, walkways, alleys, parks and vacant lots. In the more affluent countries manual street sweeping has virtually disappeared but it still commonly takes place in developing countries, where littering of public places is a far more widespread and acute problem. Mechanized street sweeping is the dominant practice in the developed countries. Street wastes include paper, cardboard, plastic, dirt, dust, leaves and other vegetable matter.

(x) Dead Animals:

This is a term applied to dead animals that die naturally or accidentally killed. This category does not include carcass and animal parts from slaughterhouses which are regarded as industrial wastes. Dead animals are divided into two groups, large and small. Among the large animals are horses, cows, goats, sheep, hogs and the like. Small animals include dogs, cats, rabbits and rats. The reason for this differentiation is that large animals require special equipment for lifting and handling during their removal. If not collected promptly, dead animals are a threat to public health because they attract flies and other vermin as they putrefy. Their presence in public places is particularly offensive and emits foul smell from the aesthetic point of view.

(xi) Construction and Demolition Wastes:

Construction and demolition wastes are the waste materials generated by the construction, refurbishment, repair and demolition of houses, commercial buildings and other structures. It mainly consists of earth, stones, concrete, bricks, lumber, roofing materials, plumbing materials, heating systems and electrical wires and parts of the general municipal waste stream, but when generated in large amounts at building and demolition sites, it is generally removed by contractors for filling low lying areas and by urban local bodies for disposal at landfills.

(xii) Industrial Wastes:

In the category are the discarded solid material of manufacturing processes and industrial operations. They cover a vast range of substances which are unique to each industry. For this reason they are considered separately from municipal wastes. It should be noted, however, that solid wastes from small industrial plants and ash from power plants are frequently disposed of at municipal landfills.

(xiii) Hazardous Wastes:

Hazardous wastes may be defined as wastes of industrial, institutional or consumer origin which, because of their physical, chemical or biological characteristics are potentially dangerous to human and the environment. In some cases although the active agents may be liquid or gaseous, they are classified as solid wastes because they are confined in solid containers. Typical examples are: solvents, paints and pesticides whose spent containers are frequently mixed with municipal wastes and become part of the urban waste stream. Certain hazardous wastes cause explosions in incinerators and fires at landfill sites. Others, such as pathological wastes from hospitals and radioactive wastes, require special handling at all time. Good management practice should ensure that hazardous wastes are stored, collected, transported and disposed off separately, preferably after suitable treatment to render them innocuous.

(xiv) Sewage Wastes:

The solid by-products of sewage treatment are classified as sewage wastes. They are mostly organic and derive from the treatment of organic sludge from both the raw and treated sewage. The inorganic fraction of raw sewage such as grit is separated at the preliminary stage of treatment, but because it entrains putrescible organic matter which may contain pathogens, must be buried/disposed off without delay. The bulk of treated, dewatered sludge is useful as a soil conditioner but invariably its use for this purpose is uneconomical. The solid sludge therefore enters the stream of municipal wastes unless special arrangements are made for its disposal.

MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE

Municipal Solid waste is defined to include refuse from households, non-hazardous solid waste from industrial, commercial and institutional establishments, market waste, yard waste and street sweepings. Semisolid wastes such as sludge and night soil are considered to be the responsibility of liquid waste management systems. While hazardous industrial and medical wastes are, by definition, not components of municipal solid waste, they are normally quite difficult to separate from municipal solid waste, particularly when their sources are small and scattered.

The sight of a dustbin overflowing and the stench rising from it are all too familiar sights and smells of a crowded city. You look away from it and hold your nose as you cross it. Have you ever thought that you also have a role to play in the creation of this stench? That you can also play a role in the lessening of this smell and making this waste bin look a little more attractive if you follow proper methods of disposal of the waste generated in the house?

Since the beginning, humankind has been generating waste, be it the bones and other parts of animals they slaughter for their food or the wood they cut to make their carts. With the progress of civilization, the waste generated became of a more complex nature. At the end of the 19th century the industrial revolution saw the rise of the world of consumers. Not only did the air get more and more polluted but the earth itself became more polluted with the generation of non-biodegradable solid waste. The increase in population and urbanization was also largely responsible for the increase in Municipal solid waste. Consists of household waste, construction

and demolition debris, sanitation residue, and waste from streets. With urbanization and change in lifestyle and food habits, the amount of municipal solid waste has been increasing rapidly and its composition changing. In 1947 cities and towns in India generated an estimated 6MT of solid waste; in 1997 it was about 48MT. More than 25% of the municipal solid waste is not collected at all; 70% of the Indian cities lack adequate capacity to transport it and there are no sanitary landfills to dispose of the waste. The existing landfills are neither well equipped nor well managed and are not lined properly to protect against contamination of soil and ground water.

CONTENTS OF THE MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE:

Urban MSW contains about 46.5% of organic matter, 6% of paper, 0.7% glass, 3.2% logs, 1% plastics and about 43% moisture. The organic content of the refuse are routinely recovered and reused but emphasis needs to be given on utilization of organic portion through composting, incineration, pyrolysis and sanitary landfills with biogas recovery.

Physical Characteristics of Municipal Solid Waste in Indian Cities

Populati on in million	Paper	Rubber, leather	Glass	Metal	Total compostable matter	Inert material
2.0 – 5.0	3.18	0.48	0.48	0.59	56.67	40.07
Above 5.0	6.43	0.28	0.94	0.80	30.84	53.90

Technologies available for Processing, Treatment and Disposal of Solid Waste

The main technological options available for processing/ treatment and disposal of MSW are composting, vermicomposting, anaerobic digestion/biomethanation, incineration, gasification and pyrolysis. Not all technologies are equally good. Each one of them has advantages and limitations.

Composting: -

Composting is a technology known in India since times immemorial. Composting is the decomposition of organic matter by microorganism in warm, moist, aerobic and anaerobic environment. Main advantages of composting include improvement in soil texture and augmenting of micronutrient deficiencies. It also increases moisture-holding capacity of the soil and helps in maintaining soil health. Moreover, it is an age-old established concept for recycling nutrients to the soil. It is simple and straightforward to adopt, for source separated MSW. It does not require large capital investment, compared to other waste treatment options. The technology is scale neutral.

This method, however, is not very suitable for wastes that may be too wet and during heavy rains open compost plants have to be stopped. Land required for open compost plants is relatively large. Also, issues of methane emission, odour, and flies from badly managed open compost plants remain. At the operational level, if waste segregation at source is not properly carried out there is possibility of toxic material entering the stream of MSW. It is essential that compost produced be safe for application. Standardization of compost quality is, therefore, necessary.

Vermicomposting: -

Vermi-compost is the natural organic manure produced from the excreta of earthworms fed on scientifically semi-decomposed organic waste. Normally, vermi-composting is preferred to microbial composting in small towns as it requires less mechanization and it is easy to operate. It is, however, to be ensured that toxic material does not enter the chain which if present could kill the earthworms.

Waste to energy: -

The main factors that determine the techno-economic viability of WTE projects are quantum of investment, scale of operation, availability of quality waste, statutory requirements and project risks. WTE projects generally involve higher capital investment and are more complex when compared to other options of waste disposal, but as pointed by Ministry of Non-Conventional Energy Sources (MNES), gains in terms of waste reduction, energy, etc. are also higher. Such plants are financially viable in developed countries mainly because of the tipping fees/gate fees charged by the facility for the service of waste disposal, in addition to its revenue income from power sales. It is thereafter the sole responsibility of the facility operator to treat and dispose of the accepted waste as per statutory requirements. However, at present in India, revenue from power sales is the only source of revenue for WTE plants.

Anaerobic Digestion and Biomethanation: -

Biomethanation is a comparatively well-established technology for disinfections, deodorization and stabilization of sewage sludge, farmyard manures, animal slurries, and industrial sludge. Its application to the organic fraction of MSW is more recent and less extensive. It leads to bio-gas/power generation in addition to production of compost (residual sludge). This method provides a value addition to the aerobic (composting) process and also offers certain other clear advantages over composting in terms of energy production/consumption, compost quality and net environmental gains.

This method is suitable for kitchen wastes and, other putrescible wastes, which may be too wet and lacking in structure for aerobic composting. It is a net energy-producing process (100–150 kWh per tonne of waste input). A totally enclosed system enables all the gas produced to be collected for use. A modular construction of plant and closed treatment needs less land area. This plant is free from bad odour, rodent and fly menace, visible pollution, and social resistance. It has potential for co-disposal with other organic waste streams from agro-based industry. The plant can be scaled up depending on the availability of the waste. However, this method is suitable for only the organic biodegradable fraction of MSW; it does not degrade any complex organics or oils, grease, or ligno-cellulosic materials such as yard waste. Similar to the aerobic composting process input waste needs to be segregated for improving digestion efficiency (biogas yield) and the quality of residual sludge. While the liquid sludge can be used as rich organic manure, either directly or after drying, its quality needs to be ensured to meet statutory standards. No grinding of waste material should take place. Wastewater generated in the plant requires treatment before disposal to meet statutory standards. Biogas leakage poses a small environmental and fire hazard. This plant is more capital intensive than aerobic composting.

Incineration: -

This method, commonly used in developed countries is most suitable for high calorific value waste with a large component of paper, plastic, packaging material, pathological wastes, etc. It can reduce waste volumes by over 90 per cent and convert waste to innocuous material, with energy recovery. The method is relatively hygienic, noiseless, and odourless, and land requirements are minimal. The plant can be located within city limits, reducing the cost of waste transportation.

This method, however, is least suitable for disposal of chlorinated waste and aqueous/high moisture content/low calorific value waste as supplementary fuel may be needed to sustain combustion, adversely affecting net energy recovery. The plant requires large capital and entails substantial operation and maintenance costs. Skilled personnel are required for plant operation and maintenance. Emission of particulates, SO_x, NO_x, chlorinated compounds in air and toxic metals in particulates concentrated in the ash have raised concerns.

Pyrolysis: -

Pyrolysis gasification processes are established for homogenous organic matter like wood, pulp, etc., while plasma pyrolysis vitrification is a relatively new technology for disposal of particularly hazardous wastes, radioactive wastes, etc. Toxic materials get encapsulated in vitreous mass, which is relatively much safer to handle than incinerator/gasifier ash. These are now being offered as an attractive option for disposal of MSW also. In all these processes, besides net energy recovery, proper destruction of the waste is also ensured. These processes, therefore, have an edge over incineration. This process produces fuel gas/fuel oil, which replace fossil fuels and compared to incineration, atmospheric pollution can be controlled at the plant level. NO and SO gas emissions do not occur in normal operations due to the lack of oxygen in the system.

Sanitary Landfills and Landfill Gas Recovery: -

Sanitary landfills are the ultimate means of disposal of all types of residual, residential, commercial and institutional waste as well as unutilized municipal solid waste from waste processing facilities and other types of inorganic waste and inerts that cannot be reused or recycled in the foreseeable future. Its main advantage is that it is the least cost option for waste disposal and has the potential for the recovery of landfill gas as a source of energy, with net environmental gains if organic wastes are land-filled. The gas after necessary cleaning can be utilized for power generation or as domestic fuel for direct thermal applications¹. Highly skilled personnel are not required to operate a sanitary landfill. Major limitation of this method is the costly transportation of MSW to far away landfill sites. Down gradient surface water can be polluted by surface run-off in the absence of proper drainage systems and groundwater aquifers may get contaminated by polluted leachate in the absence of a proper leachate collection and treatment system. An inefficient gas recovery process emits two major green house gases, carbon dioxide and methane, into the atmosphere. It requires large land area.

FUNCTIONAL ELEMENTS OF MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

The activities associated with the management of municipal solid wastes from the point of generation to final disposal can be grouped into the six functional elements:

- Waste handling and sorting, storage, and processing at the source
- Collection
- Sorting, processing and transformation
- Transfer and transport and
- Disposal.

WASTE GENERATION:

Waste generation encompasses activities in which materials are identified as no longer being of value (in their present form) and are either thrown away or gathered together for disposal. Waste generation is, at present, an activity that is not very controllable. In the future, however, more control is likely to be exercised over the generation of wastes. Reduction of waste at source, although not controlled by solid waste managers, is now included in system evaluations as a method of limiting the quantity of waste generated.

WASTE HANDLING, SORTING, STORAGE, AND PROCESSING AT THE SOURCE:

The second of the six functional elements in the solid waste management system is waste handling, sorting, storage, and processing at the source. Waste handling and sorting involves the activities associated with management of wastes until they are placed in storage containers for collection. Handling also encompasses the movement of loaded containers to the point of collection. Sorting of waste components is an important step in the handling and storage of solid waste at the source. For example, the best place to separate waste materials for reuse and recycling is at the source of generation. Households are becoming more aware of the importance of separating newspaper and cardboard, bottles/glass, kitchen wastes and ferrous and non-ferrous materials.

On-site storage is of primary importance because of public health concerns and aesthetic consideration. Unsightly makeshift containers and even open ground storage, both of which are undesirable, are often seen at many residential and commercial sites. The cost of providing storage for solid wastes at the source is normally borne by the household in the case of individuals, or by the management of commercial and industrial properties.

COLLECTION:

The functional element of collection includes not only the gathering of solid wastes and recyclable materials, but also the transport of these materials, after collection, to the location where the collection vehicle is emptied. This location may be materials processing facility, a transfer station, or a landfill disposal site.

Sorting, Processing and Transformation of Solid Waste: The sorting, processing and transformation of solid waste materials is the fourth of the functional elements. The recovery of sorted materials, processing of solid waste and transformation of solid waste that occurs primarily in locations away from the source of waste generation are encompassed by this functional element. Sorting of commingled (mixed) wastes usually occurs at a materials recovery facility, transfer stations, combustion facilities, and disposal sites. Sorting often includes the separation of bulky items, separation of waste components by size using screens, manual separation of waste components, and separation of ferrous and non-ferrous metals. Waste processing is undertaken to recover conversion products and energy. The organic fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) can be transformed by a variety of biological and thermal processes. The most commonly used biological transformation process is aerobic composting. The most commonly used thermal transformation process is incineration.

Waste transformation is undertaken to reduce the volume, weight, size or toxicity of waste without resource recovery. Transformation may be done by a variety of mechanical (e.g. shredding), thermal (e.g. incineration without energy recovery) or chemical (e.g. encapsulation) techniques.

TRANSFER AND TRANSPORT:

The functional element of transfer and transport involves two steps:

- The transfer of wastes from the smaller collection vehicle to the larger transport equipment and
- The subsequent transport of the wastes, usually over long distances, to a processing or disposal site. The transfer usually takes place at a transfer station.

DISPOSAL:

The final functional element in the solid waste management system is disposal. Today the disposal of wastes by land filling or uncontrolled dumping is the ultimate fate of all solid wastes, whether they are residential wastes collected and transported directly to a landfill site, residual materials from Materials Recovery Facilities (MRFs), residue from the combustion of solid waste, rejects of composting, or other substances from various solid waste-processing facilities. A municipal solid waste landfill plant is an engineered facility used for disposing of solid wastes on land or within the earth's mantle without creating nuisance or hazard to public health or safety, such as breeding of rodents and insects and contamination of groundwater.

CONCEPTS IN MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

- ✓ **Waste reduction:** All means of reducing the amounts of waste that must be collected and disposed of by solid waste authorities. It ranges from legislation and agreements at the national level for packaging and product redesign to local programs to prevent recyclables and compostable organics from entering final waste streams.
- ✓ **Source reduction:** Any procedure to reduce wastes at the point of generation, in contrast to sorting out recyclable components after they have been mixed together for collection.
- ✓ **Source separation:** Keeping different categories of recyclables and organics separate at source, i.e. at the point of generation, to facilitate reuse, recycling, and composting.
- ✓ **Waste recovery, materials recovery, or waste diversion:** Obtaining materials/organics (by source separation or sorting out from mixed wastes) that can be reused or recycled.
- ✓ **Reuse:** Reusing a product for the same or a different purpose

- ✓ **Recycling:** The process of transforming materials into secondary resources for manufacturing new products is called recycling.

- ✓ **Redemption center:** Waste trading enterprise that buys recyclable materials and sells to brokers. Sometimes also called "buy-back centre".

- ✓ **Producer responsibility:** Producers of products or services accept a degree of responsibility for the wastes that result from the products/services they market, by reducing materials used in production, making repairable/recyclable goods, and/or reducing packaging.

HIERARCHY OF WASTE

The waste hierarchy classifies different solid waste according to their degradability and hazardousness. The term '4 Rs', or 'Reduce-Reuse-Recycle-Respond', is been used for management of all kinds of solid waste. The waste hierarchy has taken many forms over the past decade, but the basic concept has remained the foundation stone for most of the waste minimization strategies. Waste hierarchy endeavor to have less generation of waste and more amounts of useful products from the collected solid waste.

In waste hierarchy first choice is give for reduction and reuse, Minimal preference to Recycling and composting and Land filling and incineration is not preferred as it creates pollution in the environment.

HIERARCHY OF WASTE MANAGEMENT OPTIONS

Current thinking on the best methods to deal with waste is centered on a broadly accepted 'hierarchy of waste management' (arrangement in order of rank) which gives a priority listing of the waste management options available. The hierarchy gives important general guidelines on the relative desirability of the different management options.

The hierarchy usually adopted is

- Waste minimization/reduction at source,
- Recycling,
- Waste processing (with recovery of resources i.e. materials (products) and energy),
- Waste transformation (without recovery of resources) and
- Disposal on land (land filling).

COMPOSTING

INTRODUCTION

The organic content of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) tends to decompose leading to various smell and odour problems. It also leads to pollution of the environment. To ensure a safe disposal of the MSW it is desirable to reduce its pollution potential and several processing methods are proposed for this purpose. The process results in conservation of natural resources and is an important processing method, especially in agricultural and horticultural areas. In the case of individual households, small establishments and colonies, vermi-composting which involves the stabilization of organic solid waste through earthworm consumption for conversion of the organic material to worm casting is being increasingly preferred. Organic matter constitutes 35%–40% of the municipal solid waste generated in India. This waste can be recycled by the method of composting, one of the oldest forms of disposal. It is the natural process of decomposition of organic waste that yields manure or compost, which is very rich in nutrients.

Composting is a biological process in which micro-organisms, mainly fungi and bacteria, convert degradable organic waste into humus like substance. This finished product, which looks like soil, is high in carbon and nitrogen and is an excellent medium for growing plants. The process of composting ensures the waste that is produced in the kitchens is not carelessly thrown and left to rot. It recycles the nutrients and returns them to the soil as nutrients. Apart from being clean, cheap, and safe, composting can significantly reduce the amount of disposable garbage. The organic fertilizer can be used instead of chemical fertilizers and is better specially when used for vegetables. It increases the soil's ability to hold water and makes the soil easier to cultivate. It helps the soil retain more of the plant nutrients.

EXACTLY WHAT IS COMPOSTING?

The mixing of decaying organic matter from leaves, grass clippings, manure, fruit/vegetable peelings and numerous other sources to provide a rich combination of nutrients for soils. Composting is an excellent method for farmers and gardeners to recycle material from farmlands and gardens to enrich soils and simultaneously reduce the amount of material sent to local landfills. Organic compost is ideal for use in both flower and vegetable gardens, especially during the spring and fall months. When processed correctly, compost can be added to your garden and pots to be used as topsoil.

Almost up to 30% of what goes into landfills is actually raw materials, could easily be combined to form organic rich compost for use on farms and home gardens. It's amazing to see how many people dump literally millions of tons of raw materials, which could otherwise be used for composting. Despite this fact, many consumers are becoming aware of some simple steps they can follow to make the composting process easy with minimal time and effort. Once learned, composting can reap significant benefits for consumers without having to purchase processed fertilizers, which usually lack a complete set of plant nutrients essential for optimal growth.

PRINCIPLES OF COMPOSTING

Decomposition and stabilization of organic waste matter is a natural phenomenon. Composting is an organized method of producing compost manure by adopting this natural phenomenon. Compost is particularly useful as organic manure which contains plant nutrients (Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium) as well as micro nutrients which can be utilized for the growth of plants (Gotaas 1956). When used in conjunction with chemical fertilizers optimum results are obtained.

Composting can be carried out in two ways i.e., aerobically and anaerobically. During aerobic composting aerobic micro-organisms oxidize organic compounds to Carbon dioxide, Nitrite and Nitrate. Carbon from organic compounds is used as a source of energy while nitrogen is recycled. Due to exothermic reaction, temperature of the mass rises. During anaerobic process, the anaerobic micro-organisms, while metabolizing the nutrients, break down the organic compounds through a process of reduction. A very small amount of energy is released during the process and the temperature of composting mass does not rise much. The gases evolved are mainly Methane and Carbon dioxide. An anaerobic process is a reduction process and the final product is subjected to some minor oxidation when applied to land.

METHODOLOGY

The organic material present in Municipal Waste can be converted into a stable mass by aerobic decomposition. Aerobic micro organisms oxidize organic compounds to Carbon dioxide and oxides of Nitrogen and Carbon from organic compounds is used as a source of energy, while Nitrogen is recycled. Due to exothermic reactions, temperature of mass rises. In areas/regions where higher ambient temperatures are available, composting in open windrows is to be preferred.

In the method followed in VJTI Hostel, the waste was transferred to a cement concrete tank (1.57m x 1.32m x .73m) constructed in the backyard. The initial weight of the waste (approximately 180 kg.) littered to the tank was noted. The waste was laid properly in the tank in a layer 15cm thick and covered with grass and dry tree leaves to avoid odour problems. The waste was left for pre-composting for 15 days and water was allowed to drain out of the waste. Cowdung slurry was spread thoroughly on the waste every 3rd day and the waste was turned upside down for aeration purposes.

The waste after pre-composting was mixed with cowdung and soil in ratio 75% (waste) to 25% (soil + cowdung). The density of the waste was calculated and the bed was designed. This bed was turned on every 5th day outside to centre to destroy insects' larvae and to provide aeration. Thus this process was continued till 60 days. Every alternate day water (approx. 5L) is sprinkled to maintain moisture.

FIG: AEROBIC COMPOSTING PIT SETUP AT VJTI HOSTELS

On the 60th day, the bed was broken down and passed through manually operated rotary screens of about 25mm square mesh to remove over sized contrary material. The screened compost is stored for about 30 days in heaps about 2m wide x 1.5m high and up to 20m long to ensure stabilization before use.

The place selected for composting should be usually cool. The depth provided was comfortably low so that the tank remains aerated. The pit was also lined with brick to avoid nitrite pollution of subsoil water, which is highly toxic. Each time organic matter was added to the pit it was covered with a layer of dried leaves or a thin layer of soil which allowed air to enter the pit thereby preventing bad odour. Boric powder was also laid surrounding the bed to avoid interference of ants and insects into the bed.

The pH value and moisture content of the pit were well maintained. A regular check for values of pH, moisture content and organic content was carried out.

REPORTS OF AEROBIC COMPOSTING IN VJTI HOSTELS

Sr. no.	Day	Moisture content	Organic content	pH	Temperature 0C		
					Ambient	Bed	Difference
1	1 st	58.28	65.37	6.0	27.00	24.00	-3.00
2	4 th	56.74	64.86	6.0	27.00	26.00	-1.00
4	7 th	57.70	64.26	5.5	31.00	27.00	-4.00
5	10 th	55.10	63.58	5.5	32.00	29.00	-3.00
7	13 th	58.27	62.48	6.0	32.00	36.00	4.00
8	16 th	54.12	62.07	6.5	33.00	38.00	2.00
10	19 th	56.20	60.97	7.0	28.00	35.00	7.00
11	22 th	54.29	60.05	7.5	33.00	39.00	6.00
13	25 th	51.34	59.74	7.5	32.00	38.00	6.00
14	28 th	50.87	58.27	8.0	26.00	37.00	9.00
16	31 st	49.65	57.35	8.5	28.00	39.00	9.00
17	34 th	47.25	56.14	8.0	27.00	43.00	16.00
19	37 th	47.28	55.95	7.5	26.00	47.00	21.00
20	40 th	48.89	55.02	7.5	25.00	51.00	26.00
22	43 th	44.42	54.80	7.0	26.00	54.00	28.00
23	46 th	43.07	53.60	7.0	28.00	49.00	21.00
24	49 th	41.86	52.37	7.5	30.00	45.00	15.00
25	52 th	40.97	51.80	7.5	29.00	41.00	12.00
26	55 th	40.34	50.13	7.0	31.00	43.00	12.00
27	58 th	40.03	49.53	7.0	35.00	40.00	5.00
28	60 th	39.82	48.26	7.0	34.00	38.00	4.00

Change in pH

Change in Organic Content

Change in Moisture Content

Change in Temperature

FACTORS AFFECTING THE COMPOSTING PROCESS

1] Organisms:-

Aerobic composting is a dynamic system wherein bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi and other biological forms are actively involved. The relative preponderance of one species over another depends upon the constantly changing food supply, temperature and substrate conditions. Facultative and obligate forms of bacteria, actinomycetes and fungi are most active in this process. In the initial stages mesophilic forms predominate and thermophilic bacteria and fungi soon take over except in the final stage of composting. Except when the temperature drops, actinomycetes and fungi are confined to 5 to 15 cm outer surface layer. If the turning is not carried out frequently the actinomycetes and fungi in these layers register increased growth imparting it typical grayish white colour. Thermophilic actinomycetes and fungi are known to grow well in the range of 45 to 60°C. Different organisms are known to play predominant role in breaking down different constituents of municipal solid waste. Thermophilic bacteria are mainly responsible for the breakdown of proteins and other readily biodegradable organic matter. Fungi and actinomycetes play an important role in the decomposition of cellulose and lignin. The actinomycetes common in compost are *Streptomyces* sp. and *Micromonospora* sp. the latter being more prevalent. The common fungi in compost are *Thermonomyces* sp., *Penicillium dupontii* and *Asperigallus fumigatus*. Majority of these organisms responsible for composting are already present in municipal solid waste. Not much information is available regarding the organisms active in anaerobic composting, though many of the organisms responsible for anaerobic decomposition of sewage sludge will be active here also, and differences are expected due to the concentration of nutrients present and the temperature conditions.

2] Moisture:-

The moisture tends to occupy the free air space between the particles. Hence, when the moisture content is very high, anaerobic conditions set in. However, the composting mass should have certain minimum moisture content in it for the organisms to survive. The optimum moisture content is known to be between 50 to 60 %. Higher moisture content may be required while composting straw and strong fibrous material which soften the fiber and fills the large pore spaces. Higher moisture content can also be used in mechanically aerated digesters. In anaerobic composting the moisture content used will depend upon the method of handling and whether it is carried out in the open or in closed container.

3] Temperature:-

The aerobic decomposition of a gram mole of glucose releases 484 to 674 kilo calories (kcal) energy under controlled conditions, while only 26 kcal are released when it is decomposed an-aerobically. Municipal solid waste is known to have good insulation properties and hence the released heat results in increase in temperature of the decomposing mass. As some of the heat loss occurs from the exposed surface, the actual rise in temperature will be slightly less. When the decomposing mass is disturbed during the turning of windrows, the resultant heat loss results in drop in temperature. Under properly controlled conditions temperatures are known to rise beyond 70°C in aerobic composting. Under properly controlled conditions temperatures are known to rise beyond 70°C in aerobic composting. During anaerobic composting as the released heat is quite small and as part of it is lost from the surface only a marginal rise in temperature occurs. This increased temperature results in increased rate of

biological activity and hence results in faster stabilization of the material. However, if the temperature rise is very high, due to inactivation of the organisms & enzymes the rate of activity may decrease. The studies carried out have shown that the activity of cellulose enzyme reduces above 70°C and the optimum temperature range for nitrification is 30° to 50°C beyond which nitrogen loss is known to occur. The temperature range of 50° to 60°C is thus optimum for nitrification and cellulose degradation. The high temperature also helps in destruction of some common pathogens and parasites (Table 14.1). According to Scott, during aerobic composting when the material is turned twice in 12 days *Entamoeba histolytica* is killed and the eggs of *Ascaris lumbricoides* are killed in 36 days when turned thrice. The studies carried out at NEERI have shown that the destruction of these organisms is not ensured under anaerobic conditions. Knoll has proved that the high temperature and long retention during aerobic composting along with the antibiotic effect results in destruction of parasites and pathogens. Thus, if the process is so controlled that the temperature is kept between 50° to 60°C for 5 to 7 days, destruction of pathogens and parasites can be ensured.

4] Carbon/Nitrogen (C/N) Ratio:-

The organisms involved in stabilization of organic matter utilize about 30 parts of carbon for each part of nitrogen and hence an initial C/N ratio of 30 is most favorable for composting. Research workers have reported the optimum value to range between 26 and 31 depending upon other environmental conditions. The C/N ratio considers the available carbon as well as the available nitrogen while the available carbon and nitrogen in the MSW may vary from sample to sample. Whenever the C/N ratio is less than the optimum, carbon source such as straw, sawdust, paper are added while if the ratio is too high, the sewage sludge, slaughter house waste, blood etc. are added as a source of nitrogen.

5] Aeration:-

It is necessary to ensure that oxygen is supplied throughout the mass and aerobic activity is maintained. During the decomposition, the oxygen gets depleted and has to be continuously replenished. This can be achieved either by turning of windrows or by supplying compressed air. During the turning, it is necessary to bring inner mass to the outer surface and to transfer the outer waste to the inner portion. In case of artificial air supply the quantity of air supply is normally maintained at 1-2 cu.m./day/kg of volatile solids. Artificial air supply requires enclosing decomposing mass in containers which is quite costly. Hence in Indian conditions the decomposition is commonly carried out in open windrows. Studies at NEERI have shown that the optimum turning interval which will reduce the cost and simultaneously maintain aerobic conditions is 5 days.

6] Properties of Compost

The compost prepared from MSW should be black brown or at least black in colour. It should be crumbly in nature with an earthy odour. The pH should be neutral though slightly acidic or alkaline pH within the range of 6.5 to 7.5 can be tolerated. The compost should neither be completely dry nor it be lumpy and water should not come out of the mass when squeezed. The Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium (NPK) contents should be more than one percent each. The Nitrogen should be in the form of Nitrates for proper utilization by the plants. The C/N ratio should be between 15 and 20.

Composting: some benefits

- ✓ Compost allows the soil to retain more plant nutrients over a longer period.
- ✓ It supplies part of the 16 essential elements needed by the plants.
- ✓ It helps reduce the adverse effects of excessive alkalinity, acidity, or the excessive use of chemical fertilizer.
- ✓ It makes soil easier to cultivate.
- ✓ It helps keep the soil cool in summer and warm in winter.
- ✓ It aids in preventing soil erosion by keeping the soil covered.
- ✓ It helps in controlling the growth of weeds in the garden.

VERMICOMPOSTING

WHAT IS VERMICOMPOSTING?

With the need to divert increasing amounts of household biodegradable waste from landfill, more emphasis needs to be placed on composting suitable wastes such as kitchen waste. There would appear to be enormous potential to transform these types of wastes into high specification compost products, especially innovative methods of stabilizing and maturing waste, such as vermicomposting, are becoming established. The capacity of vermicomposting to produce low particle size compost is an important observation and would appear to present waste managers with an effective way of amending and enhancing the characteristics of screened compost products through the inclusion of appropriate waste types in the composting mix.

Vermicomposting involves the stabilization of organic solid waste through earthworm consumption which converts the material into worm castings. Vermicomposting is the result of combined activity of microorganisms and earthworms. Microbial decomposition of biodegradable organic matter occurs through extra cellular enzymatic activities (primary decomposition) whereas decomposition in earthworm occurs in alimentary tract by microorganisms inhabiting the gut (secondary decomposition). Microbes such as fungi, actinomycetes, protozoa etc. are reported to inhabit the gut of earthworms. Ingested feed substrates are subjected to grinding in the anterior part of the worms gut (gizzard) resulting in particle size reduction.

Vermitechnology, a tripartite system which involves biomass, microbes and earthworms is influenced by the abiotic factors such as temperature, moisture, aeration etc. Microbial ecology changes according to change of abiotic factors in the biomass but decomposition never ceases. Conditions unfavourable to aerobic decomposition result in mortality of earthworms and subsequently no vermicomposting occurs. Hence, preprocessing of the waste as well as providing favourable environmental condition is necessary for vermicomposting. The vermicompost is relatively more stabilized and harmonizes with soil system without any ill effects. Unfavourable conditions such as particle size of biomass and extent of its decomposition, very large temperature increase, anaerobic condition, toxicity of decomposition products etc. influence activity of worms. This technology has been used for agricultural waste and its adoption to municipal solid waste is of recent origin.

Vermicompost contains not only worm castings, but also bedding materials and organic wastes at various stages of decomposition. It also contains worms at various stages of development and other microorganisms associated with the composting processing. Earthworm castings in the home garden often contain 5 to 11 times more nitrogen, phosphorous, and potassium as the surrounding soil. Secretions in the intestinal tracts of earthworms, along with soil passing through the earthworms, make nutrients more concentrated and available for plant uptake, including micronutrients. Red-worms in vermicompost act in a similar fashion, breaking down food wastes and other organic residues into nutrient-rich compost.

Finished vermicompost should have a rich, earthy smell if properly processed by worms. Vermicompost can be used in potting soil mixes for house plants and as a top dressing for lawns. Screened vermicompost combined with potting soil mixes make an excellent medium for starting young seedlings. Vermicompost also makes an excellent mulch and soil conditioner for the home garden.

WHY VERMICOMPOSTING? WHAT ARE ITS UNIQUE BENEFITS?

Vermicomposting

The Worms do the
Work for you!

WHY?

Aerators

Worms add Oxygen
for all the beneficial
micro-organisms.

Turners

Like Tiny Plows,
worms work throughout
the material

Mixers

Worms move all kinds of
organisms and nutrients
throughout the compost pile
adding many
small aggregates.

Screeners

Worms eat the bedding
materials and the feed
and turn it into
a rich soil product.

Pathogen Controllers

Worms ingest and render
useless, the "bad guys".

Accelerators

Worms can eat 1/2 to all their weight per day.
A 5'x8' large scale Flow-through system
can process 100 lbs of food scraps per day
and will produce 78-80 lbs of castings per day.

UNIQUE BENEFITS OF VERMICOMPOSTING: -

a. **TURN**: Like tiny plows, they work their way throughout the material.

b. **AERATE**: They add oxygen for all the beneficial microorganisms.

c. **MIX**: All kinds of organisms and nutrients throughout the pile adding lots of small aggregates.

d. **SCREEN**: They eat the bedding materials and the feed, ultimately turning it into a rich soil product.

e. **PATHOGEN CONTROL**: They ingest and render useless the “bad guys”.

f. **FAST**: They can eat one-half of their weight per day. 5' x 8' Large Scale Flow Through System can process 100lb food scraps per day and 75-80 lbs. of castings per day

WHY WORM CASTINGS ARE BETTER THAN COMPOST?

Growers Prefer Worm Castings Over Compost

Because research shows
Worm Castings Produce Superior Results

ADVANTAGES OF WORM CASTINGS OVER COMPOST –

- ✓ **Higher concentrations of microorganisms.**
- ✓ **More diversity of microorganisms.**
- ✓ **Enzymes and plant growth regulators only found in worm casting soils.**
- ✓ **Higher percentage of available nutrients.**
- ✓ **Greater plant heights leaf area and root depth.**
- ✓ **Greater germination rates.**
- ✓ **Faster growth rates.**
- ✓ **Higher aggregate formation.**
- ✓ **Better disease control.**
- ✓ **Higher capacity to hold water.**
- ✓ **More nutrient availability over time.**
- ✓ **Larger fruits and vegetables with higher yields.**
- ✓ **Sweeter tasting fruits and abundantly richer tasting vegetables.**

TYPES OF EARTHWORMS

Earthworms are invertebrates. There are nearly 3600 types of earthworms in the world and they are mainly divided into two types:

- (1) Burrowing;
- (2) Non-Burrowing.

The burrowing types **Pertima elongata** and **Pertima asiatica** live deep in the soil. On the other hand, the non-burrowing types **Eisenia foetida** and **Eudrilus eugeniae** live in the upper layer of soil surface. The burrowing types are pale, 20 to 30 cm long and live for 15 years. The non-burrowing types are red or purple and 10 to 15 cm long but their life span is only 28 months. The non-burrowing earthworms eat 10% soil and 90% organic waste materials; these convert the organic waste into vermicompost faster than the burrowing earthworms. They can tolerate temperatures ranging from 0 to 40°C but the regeneration capacity is more at 25 to 30°C and 40–45% moisture level in the pile. The burrowing type of earthworms comes onto the soil surface only at night. These make holes in the soil up to a depth of 3.5 m and produce 5.6 kg casts by ingesting 90% soil and 10% organic waste.

The most common types of earthworms used for vermicomposting are **Brandling-worms** (*Eisenia foetida*) and **Red-worms** or **Red Wigglers** (*Lumbricus rubellus*). Often found in aged manure piles, they generally have alternating red and buff-colored stripes. They are not to be confused with the common garden or field earthworm (*Allolobophora Caliginosa* and other species). Although the garden earthworm occasionally feeds on the bottom of a compost pile, they prefer ordinary soil. An acre of land can have as many as 500,000 earthworms, which can recycle as much as 5 tons of soil or more per year. Red-worms and brandling worms, however, prefer the compost or manure environment. Passing through the gut of the earthworm, recycled organic wastes are excreted as castings, or worm manure, an organic material rich in nutrients that looks like fine-textured soil.

ANATOMY OF EARTHWORMS

The earthworm has a long, rounded body with a pointed head and slightly flattened posterior. Rings that surround the moist, soft body allow the earthworm to twist and turn, especially since it has no backbone. With no true legs, bristles (setae) on the body move back and forth, allowing the earthworm to crawl. The earthworm breathes through its skin. Food is ingested through the mouth into a stomach (crop). Later the food passes through the gizzard, where it is ground up by ingested stones. After passing through the intestine for digestion, what left is eliminated. Earthworms are hermaphrodites, which mean they have both male and female sex organs, but they require another earthworm to mate. The wide band (clitella) that surrounds a mature breeding earthworm secretes mucus (albumin) after mating. Sperm from another worm is stored in sacs. As the mucus slides over the worm, it encases the sperm and eggs inside. After slipping free from the worm, both ends seal, forming a lemon-shape cocoon approximately 1/8 inch long. Two or more baby worms will hatch from one end of the cocoon in approximately 3 weeks. Baby worms are whitish to almost transparent and are 1/2 to 1 inch long. Red-worms take 4 to 6 weeks to become sexually mature.

MATERIALS REQUIRED FOR VERMICOMPOSTING

A range of agricultural residues, all dry wastes, for example, sorghum straw and rice straw (after feeding cattle), dry leaves of crops and trees, pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan*) stalks, groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) husk, soybean residues, vegetable wastes, weed (*Parthenium*) plants before flowering, fiber from coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) trees and sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum*) trash can be converted into vermicompost. In addition, animal manures, dairy and poultry wastes, food industry wastes, municipal solid wastes, biogas sludge and bagasse from sugarcane factories also serve as good raw materials for vermicomposting.

The quantity of raw materials required using a cement ring of 90 cm in diameter and 30 cm in height or a pit or tank measuring 1.5 m × 1 m × 1 m is given below:

- | | | |
|-----------------------------|---|----------------------|
| 1. Dry organic wastes (DOW) | - | 50 kg |
| 2. Dung slurry (DS) | - | 15 kg |
| 3. Rock phosphate (RP) | - | 2 kg |
| 4. Earthworms (EW) | - | 500 – 700 Nos. |
| 5. Water (W) | - | 5 L every three days |

The various ingredients are used in the ratio of

$$\mathbf{5 : 1.5 : 0.2 : 50-75 : 0.5}$$
$$\mathbf{DOW : DS : RP : EW : W.}$$

In the tank or pit system 100 kg of raw material and 15–20 kg of cow dung are needed for each cubic meter of the bed.

Materials for preparation of Vermicompost:

1. Any types of biodegradable wastes-
2. Crop residues
3. Hotel refuse
4. Weed biomass
5. Waste from agro-industries
6. Vegetable waste
7. Biodegradable portion of urban and rural wastes
8. Leaf litter
9. Egg shells and Meat.

NOT to Compost

1. Pet Wastes
2. Diseased Plants
3. Human wastes
4. Pernicious weeds
5. Chemically treated wood products

HOW TO CONSTRUCT A WORM BIN

Bins can be made of wood or plastic, or from recycled containers like old bathtubs, barrels, or trunks. They also can be located inside or outside, depending your preferences and circumstances. As red wigglers tend to be surface feeders, bins should be no more than 8 to 12 inches deep. Bedding food wastes tend to pack down in deeper bins, forcing air out. Resulting anaerobic conditions can cause foul odors and death of the worms. The length and width of the bin will depend on whether it is to be stationary or portable. It also depends on the amount of food waste your family produces each week. A good rule of thumb is to provide one square foot of surface area per pound of waste in your bin. Wooden bins have the advantage that they're more absorbent and provide better insulation. Do not use redwood or other highly aromatic woods that may kill the worms. Plastic tends to keep the compost too moist. Plastic, however, tends to be less messy and easier to maintain. Be sure containers are well cleaned and have never stored pesticides or other chemicals. Drilling air/drainage holes (1/4TH to 1/2TH -inch diameter) in the bottom and sides of the bin will ensure good water drainage and air circulation.

Place the bin on bricks or wooden blocks in a tray to catch excess water that drains from the bin. The resulting compost tea can be used as a liquid fertilizer around the home landscape. Each bin should have a cover to conserve moisture and exclude light. Worms prefer darkness. Bins can be covered with a straw mulch or moist burlap to ensure darkness while providing good air ventilation. Outside bins may require a lid to exclude scavengers and other unwanted pests. Outdoor bins should be insulated from the cold to protect the worms. One option is to dig a rectangular hole 12 inches deep and line the sides with wooden planks. The bottomless box can then be filled with appropriate

bedding material, food wastes, and worms. Food wastes can be continually added as they accumulate. The pile should be kept damp and dark for optimum worm activity. During the winter, soil can be piled against the edges of the bin and straw placed on top to protect the worms from cold weather. Do not add food waste to outdoor bins during the winter because this could expose the worms to freezing weather.

PHOTOGRAPHS SHOWING CONSTRUCTION OF THE WORM BED

Fig : Laying soil in the pit

Fig: Bed of soil and pre-composted waste

Fig: Mixing of cow-dung and soil

Fig : Bed with top layer of cow-dung

Fig : Worms lay over the top of bed

BEDDING MATERIALS

Bedding for bins can be made from shredded newspapers (non-glossy), computer paper, or cardboard; shredded leaves, straw, hay, or dead plants; sawdust; peat moss; or compost or aged (or composted) manure. Peat moss should be soaked for 24 hours in water, and then lightly wrung out to ensure it is sufficiently moist. Grass clippings should be allowed to age before use because they may decompose too quickly, causing the compost to heat up. Bedding materials high in cellulose are best because they help aerate the bin so the worms can breathe. Varying the bedding material provides a richer source of nutrients. Some soil or sand can be added to help provide grit for the worm's digestive systems. Allow the bedding material to set for several days to make sure it doesn't heat up (and allow to cool before adding worms). The bedding material should be thoroughly moistened (about the consistency of a damp sponge) before adding the worms. Fill the bin three-quarters full of moist bedding, lifting it gently afterwards to create air space for the worms to breathe and to control odors.

ADDING THE WORMS

Under optimum conditions, red-worms can eat their own weight in food scraps and Bedding in one day. On the average, however, it takes approximately 2 pounds of Earthworms (approximately 2,000 breeders) to recycle a pound of food waste in 24 hours. The same quantity of worms requires about 4 cubic feet of bin to process the food waste and bedding (1 cubic foot of worm bin/500 worms). Composting worms can be purchased from dealers listed in the ad sections of many garden magazines. Some dealers sell worms as pit-run worms, which consist of worms of all ages and sizes. Add worms to the top of the moist bedding when they arrive. The worms will disappear into the bedding within a few minutes.

ADDING FOOD WASTE

Earthworms eat all kinds of food and yard wastes, including coffee grounds, tea bags, vegetable and fruit waste, pulverized egg shells, grass clippings, manure, and sewage sludge. Avoid bones, dairy products, and meats that may attract pests, and garlic, onions, and spicy foods. Limited amounts of citrus can be added, but too much can make the compost too acidic. The compost should be kept at a pH of 6.5 if possible, with upper and lower limits at 7.0 and 6.0, respectively. Overly acidic compost can be corrected by adding crushed eggshells. Avoid adding chemicals (including insecticides), metals, plastics, glass, soaps, pet manures, and oleanders or other poisonous plants, or plants sprayed with insecticides to the worm bin. Food wastes should be added to the bin by pulling back the bedding material and burying it. Be sure to cover it well to avoid attracting flies and other pests. Successive loads of waste should be buried at different locations in the bin to keep the food wastes from accumulating. Grinding or blending the food waste in a food processor speeds the composting time considerably.

CONTROLLING TEMPERATURE AND MOISTURE IN THE BIN

Red-worms can survive a wide range of temperatures (40-80°F), but they reproduce and process food waste at an optimum bedding temperature range of 55-77°F. The worms should never be allowed to freeze. Bins kept outside may have to be insulated with straw in the winter to keep the worms from freezing. Portable bins can be kept by a hot water heater in the garage during the winter to keep them warm. The bin contents should be kept moist but not soaked. Do not allow rainfall to run off a roof into the bin. This could cause the worms to drown. A straw covering may be needed in exposed sites to keep the bin from drying out during hot summer weather.

MAINTAINING THE BIN

Food scraps can be continually added to the bin for up to 2 to 3 months, or until you notice the bedding material disappear. When the bedding disappears, harvest the worms and finished compost, then refill the bins with new bedding material. Overloading the bin with food wastes can result in foul odors. If you notice these odors, stop adding the waste until the worms have a chance to catch up. Overly moist food waste and bedding also cause odors. To relieve this problem, fluff up the bedding to add air and check the drainage holes. As a general rule of thumb, keep the bedding material moist, but never soggy. Make sure the food waste is buried properly in the bedding. Exposed food wastes can attract fruit flies, house flies, and other pests. Keeping the bin covered with straw or moist burlap also deters these pests. Garden centipedes can be a problem in the worm bin, especially outside. These predators should be destroyed. Overly wet beds also can attract the earthworm mite, which may cause the worms to stop eating.

HARVESTING THE COMPOST AND WORMS

There are three basic ways to separate the worms from the finished compost. One way involves moving the finished compost and worms over to one side of the bin and adding new bedding material and food waste to the other side. Worms in the finished compost should move over to the new bedding with the fresh food waste. The finished compost can then be removed. A second way to remove the worms is to build a small harvester frame of 2 x 4s with a 3/16-inch mesh bottom. Place the worm compost on the frame and shift the worms out. Larger pieces of compost can be returned to a new batch of bedding and worms. The compost also can be placed in small piles on a tarp in the sun (or under bright lights inside). Because worms don't like light, they will wiggle to the bottoms of the piles. After waiting 10 minutes, remove the upper inch or more of finished compost from each pile until you run into the worms. Allow the worms to again wiggle to the bottom of the pile and repeat the process. Combine what is left of the small piles into one big pile and again repeat the process. You should eventually end up with a pile of finished compost and a ball of worms. The worms can be added back to a new bin of bedding and food waste. Larger worms also can be used as bait for fishing.

METHODOLOGY

In the method followed in VJTI Hostel, the waste was transferred to a cement concrete tank (1.57m x 1.32m x .73m) constructed in the backyard. The initial weight of the waste (approximately 180 kg.) littered to the tank was noted. The waste was laid properly in the tank in a layer 15cm thick and covered with grass and dry tree leaves to avoid odour problems. The waste was left for pre-composting for 15 days and water was allowed to drain out of the waste. Cow-dung slurry was spread thoroughly on the waste every 3rd day and the waste was turned upside down for aeration purposes.

The density of the waste was calculated and the bed was designed. The waste after pre-composting was mixed with cow-dung and soil in ratio 75% (waste) to 25% (soil + cow-dung). Exactly 180 Worms (approx 1kg) were added through the cracks on the surface of the bed. The density of the waste was calculated and the bed was designed. This bed was turned on 30th day outside to centre to destroy insects' larvae and to provide aeration. Thus this process was continued till 60 days. Every alternate day water (approx. 5L) is sprinkled to maintain moisture.

On the 60th day, the bed was broken down and passed through manually operated rotary screens of about 25mm square mesh to remove over sized contrary material. The screened compost is stored for about 30 days in heaps about 2m wide x 1.5m high and up to 20m long to ensure stabilization before use.

The place selected for vermicomposting should be usually cool. The depth provided was comfortably low so that the tank remains aerated. Each time organic matter was added to the pit it was covered with a layer of dried leaves or a thin layer of soil which allowed air to enter the pit thereby preventing bad odour. Boric powder was also laid surrounding the bed to avoid interference of ants and insects into the bed. The pH value and moisture content of the pit were well maintained. A regular check for values of pH, moisture content and organic content was carried out.

Results obtained

The resultant values of vermicompost obtained in this study are presented in Table. The pH of soil value was 7.0. The cow dung influenced the rate of vermicompost. Hence, it is clear that the mixture of vegetable waste and cow dung is suitable for the production of higher quality vermicompost when compared with the subjecting the same components individually.

Sr. no.	Day	Moisture content	Organic content	pH	Temperature °C		
					Ambient	Bed	Difference
1	1 st	42.08	62.48	7.5	27.00	24.00	-3.00
2	4 th	44.18	62.07	7.5	27.00	26.00	-1.00
4	7 th	47.70	60.97	7.5	31.00	27.00	-4.00
5	10 th	49.10	60.00	7.0	32.00	29.00	-3.00
7	13 th	48.27	59.74	7.0	32.00	26.00	-6.00
8	16 th	45.12	58.27	6.5	33.00	28.00	-5.00
10	19 th	46.20	57.35	7.0	28.00	25.00	-3.00
11	22 th	44.29	56.14	7.0	33.00	29.00	-4.00
13	25 th	41.34	54.95	7.5	32.00	28.00	-4.00
14	28 th	40.87	54.02	7.5	26.00	27.00	1.00
16	31 th	39.65	52.80	7.5	28.00	29.00	1.00
17	34 th	37.25	51.60	7.5	27.00	28.00	1.00
19	37 th	34.28	50.37	7.0	26.00	27.00	1.00
20	40 th	35.89	48.80	7.0	25.00	27.00	2.00
22	43 th	32.42	46.13	7.0	26.00	28.00	2.00
23	45 th	32.07	43.26	7.0	28.00	29.00	1.00

Change in pH

Change in Organic content

Change in Moisture Content

Change in Temperature

FINAL COMPOST OBTAINED

The final compost obtained was a high quality manure with the properties like moisture content, organic content, pH etc. lying within the specified range. The figure below shows the Vermicompost obtained from the Vermicomposting pit set up in VJTI hostels.

FIG :THE FINAL COMPOST OBTAINED

MEASUREMENT OF PARAMETERS

Bulk Density Measurement: -

Materials and apparatus:

- Wooden box of 1 m³ capacity
- Wooden box of 0.028 m³ capacity
- Spring balance with weighing capacity of 50 kg.

Procedure:

The solid waste should be taken in the smaller 0.028 m³ box to give a composite sample, from different parts of the heap of waste, then weighed with the help of a spring balance. After weighing, this smaller box (0.028 m³) is emptied in bigger 1 m³ box and the weight of the waste poured into the bigger box is noted. This is repeated till the larger box is filled to the top. The waste should not be compacted by pressure. Fill the 1 m³ box three times and take the average. Thus the weight per cubic meter is obtained.

Moisture Content

Moisture content of solid wastes is usually expressed as the weight of moisture per unit weight of wet material.

$$\text{Moisture Content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Wet weight} - \text{Dry weight}}{\text{Wet weight}} \times 100$$

A typical range of moisture contents is 20 – 45% representing the extremes of wastes in an arid climate and in the wet season of a region having large precipitation. Values greater than 45% are however not uncommon. Moisture increases the weight of solid waste and therefore the cost of collection and transport. Consequently, waste should be insulated from rainfall or other extraneous water. Moisture content is a critical determinant in the economic feasibility of waste treatment and processing methods by incineration since energy (e.g. heat) must be supplied for evaporation of water and in raising the temperature of the water vapour. Climatic conditions apart, moisture content is generally higher in low income countries because of the higher proportion of food and yard waste.

Organic Content

The sample collected from the pit was placed in a crucible and weight was measured. This weight was marked as the initial weight (W1). This sample was then kept in the Muffle Furnace and the temperature was raised to 600°C. When the temperature reached 600°C, the furnace was switched off and the sample was allowed to cool. The organic matter in the waste burns away at 600°C. The sample is then taken out of furnace and the weight is measured. The organic content is calculated by following formula:

- Initial Weight (W1)
- Final Weight (W2)

$$\text{Organic Content (\%)} = \frac{W1 - W2}{W2} \times 100$$

Size of Waste Constituents

The size distribution of waste constituents in the waste stream is important because of its significance in the design of mechanical separators and shredder and waste treatment process. This varies widely and while designing a system, proper analysis of the waste characteristics should be carried out.

Chemical Characteristics

Knowledge of chemical characteristics of waste is essential in determining the efficacy of any treatment process. Chemical characteristics include (i) chemical; (ii) bio-chemical; and (iii) toxic.

Chemical:

Chemical characteristics include pH, Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium (N-P-K), total Carbon, C/N ratio, and calorific value.

PRECAUTIONS DURING THE PROCESS

The following precautions should be taken during vermicomposting:

- The African species of earthworms, *Eisenia foetida* and *Eudrilus eugeniae* are ideal for the preparation of vermicompost. Most Indian species are not suitable for the purpose.
- Only plant-based materials such as grass, leaves or vegetable peelings should be utilized in preparing vermicompost.
- Materials of animal origin such as eggshells, meat, bone, chicken droppings, etc are not suitable for preparing vermicompost.
- *Gliricidia* lopping and tobacco leaves are not suitable for rearing earthworms.
- The earthworms should be protected against birds, termites, ants and rats.
- Adequate moisture should be maintained during the process. Either stagnant water or lack of moisture could kill the earthworms.
- After completion of the process, the vermicompost should be removed from the bed at regular intervals and replaced by fresh waste materials.

ADVANTAGES OF VERMICOMPOST:

1. Vermicompost is rich in all essential plant nutrients.
2. Provides excellent effect on overall plant growth encourages the growth of new shoots / leaves and improves the quality and shelf life of the produce.
3. Vermicompost is free flowing, easy to apply, handle and store and does not have bad odour.
4. It improves soil structure, texture, aeration, and water holding capacity and prevents soil erosion.
5. Vermicompost is rich in beneficial micro flora such as fixers, P-solubilizers, cellulose decomposing micro-flora etc in addition to improve soil environment.
6. Vermicompost contains earthworm cocoons and increases the population and activity of earthworm in the soil.
7. It neutralizes the soil protection.
8. It prevents nutrient losses and increases the use efficiency of chemical fertilizers.
9. Vermicompost is free from pathogens, toxic elements, weed seeds etc.
10. Vermicompost minimizes the incidence of pest and diseases.
11. It enhances the decomposition of organic matter in soil.
12. It contains valuable vitamins, enzymes and hormones like auxins, gibberellins etc.

HOW TO USE VERMICOMPOST?

- Vermicompost can be used for all crops: agricultural, horticultural, ornamental and vegetables at any stage of the crop.
- For general field crops: Around 2–3 t ha⁻¹ vermicompost is used by mixing with seed at the time of sowing or by row application when the seedlings are 12–15 cm in height. Normal irrigation is followed.
- For fruit trees: The amount of vermicompost ranges from 5 to 10 kg per tree depending on the age of the plant. For efficient application, a ring (15–18 cm deep) is made around the plant. A thin layer of dry cow dung and bone meal is spread along with 2–5 kg of vermicompost and water is sprayed on the surface after covering with soil.
- For vegetables: For raising seedlings to be transplanted, vermicompost at 1 t ha⁻¹ is applied in the nursery bed. This results in healthy and vigorous seedlings. But for transplants, vermicompost at the rate of 400–500 g per plant is applied initially at the time of planting and 45 days after planting (before irrigation).
- For flowers: Vermicompost is applied at 750–1000 kg ha⁻¹.
- For vegetable and flower crops vermicompost is applied around the base of the plant. It is then covered with soil and watered regularly.

CONCLUSION

- The final compost obtained from both the pits i.e. Aerobic Composting and Vermicomposting, is a high quality manure with the properties like moisture content, organic content, pH etc. lying within the specified range.
- The study shows that the compost from the Vermicomposting Pit is better than that obtained from Aerobic Composting pit. The Vermicomposting pit has higher percentage of available nutrients and has higher capacity to hold water.
- It is my conclusion that Aerobic Composting and Vermicomposting are two methods for management of Municipal Solid (Biodegradable) Waste more economical and better than anaerobic composting. The waste can be treated effectively by these two methods without any harm to surrounding environment.

REFERENCES/BIBLIOGRAPHY:-

1. www.cpcb.com an official website of Central Pollution Control Board.
2. K. Muthukumaravel, A. Amsath and M. Sukumaran (October 2008), Vermicomposting of Vegetable Waste using Cow Dung.
3. Hand Book on Medicinal And Aromatic Plants, Vermicompost and its Utilization.
4. Manual on Municipal Solid Waste Management, the Government of India Ministry of Urban Development.
5. Municipal Solid Waste, Studies of CPCB, Best Management Practices Manual (Solid Waste Management)
6. Solid Waste Management in Developing Countries, A.D. Bhide, B. B. Sundaresan, Indian National Scientific Documentation Centre.
7. Municipal Solid Waste, Studies of CPCB. Caltrans Storms Water Quality Handbook Section 8, (March 1, 2003).
8. Management of Municipal Solid Waste, T.V. Ramachandra, Centre for Ecological Sciences, Indian Institute of Sciences, Bangalore.
9. N B Singh, Dr A K Khare, Dr D S Bhargava, S Bhattacharya,(September 2004), Effect of Substrate Depth on Vermicomposting, IE (I) Journal.EN , Vol 85

10. Amar M. Dhere, Chandrasekhar B. Pawar, Pratapsingh B. Pardeshi and Dhanraj A Patil, (25 SEPTEMBER 2008) Municipal solid waste disposal in Pune city – An analysis of air and groundwater pollution, CURRENT SCIENCE, VOL. 95, NO.6.
11. Joshua Daniel, Sucharita Dhar and Jyoti Desai (September 2005), Improving Livelihoods through Vermicomposting LEISA Magazine.
12. Aveyard Jim. 1988. Land degradation: Changing attitudes - why? Journal of Soil Conservation, New South Wales 44:46–51.
13. Bhadauria T and Ramakrishnan PS. 1996. Role of earthworms in nitrogen cycle during the cropping phase of shifting agriculture (jhum) in northeast India. Biology and Fertility of Soils 22:350–354.
14. Bhiday MR. 1994. Earthworms in agriculture. Indian Farming 43(12): 31–34.
15. Coleman D C. 1985. Through a red darkly: an ecological assessment of root soil microbial faunal interactions. Pages 1–21 in Ecological interaction in Soil (Fitter AH, Atkinson D, Read DJ and Usher MB, eds.). London, UK: Blackwell Scientific Publications.
16. Vadiraj BA, Siddagangaiah D and Potty SN. 1998. Response of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) cultivars to graded levels of vermicompost. Journal of Spices and Aromatic Crops 7(2):141–143.

17. Vermi Co. 2001. Vermicomposting technology for waste management and agriculture: an executive summary. (<http://www.vermico.com/summary.htm>) PO Box 2334, Grants Pass, OR 97528, USA: Vermi Co.
18. Wani SP. 2002. Improving the livelihoods: New partnerships for win-win solutions for natural resource management. Paper submitted in the 2nd International Agronomy Congress held at New Delhi, India during 26–30 November 2002.
19. Ranganathan LS and Vinotha SP. 1998. Influence of pressmud on the enzymatic variations in the different reproductive stages of *Eudrilus eugeniae*. *Current Science* 74: 634–635.
20. Reddy R, Reddy MAN, Reddy YTN, Reddy NS, Anjanappa N and Reddy R. 1998. Effect of organic and inorganic sources of NPK on growth and yield of pea [*Pisum sativum*(L)]. *Legume Research* 21(1):57–60.
21. Sreenivas C, Muralidhar S and Rao MS. 2000. Vermicompost, a viable component of IPNSS in nitrogen nutrition of ridge gourd. *Annals of Agricultural Research* 21(1):108–113.
22. Sunitha ND, Giraddi RS, Kulkarni KA and Lingappa S. 1997. Evaluation methods of vermicomposting under open field conditions. *Karnataka Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 10(4): 987–990.